

Study Ethics:

The study protocol was approved from the Ethics Committee of the Research Institute [NHTMRI 6-2017], approval date:18/2/2017. This research was reported on ClinicalTrials.gov with ID number: NCT03247296. This research was performed following the criteria set out in the Norms of Good Clinical Practice and the Helsinki Declaration

A written informed consents (attached plain pdf file) were reviewed, discussed and signed by the participant and clinical investigator before enrollment without any obligation on the volunteers to continue if they didn't want to.

Clinical Investigator, study director, licensed physicians responsible for documenting the patients biochemical data (attached plain pdf file) and undergoing physical examination and following-up of the subjects for appearance of any side or adverse effects, measurement of vital signs throughout the study including blood pressure, pulse rate, body temperature before and all over the study and registered nurses were responsible for blood sampling.